

Sentiment analysis in health care – an overview with the help of r software package

Abstract

With increase in online media which provides various platforms including the social media for patient to share, discuss and express their experiences related to quality of care received from the health care providers, about the healthcare professional they interacted with them, healthcare facilities they utilized. This has generated vast amount of information in the form of unstructured data which can be useful for decision making for various stakeholders in the healthcare sector. There is a need to build an analytical tool which can help us to analyze the sentiment present in the information generated from the above online sources. This paper provides an overview of sentiment analysis and builds a model to analyze the sentiments through help of R statistical software.

Keywords: Sentiment analysis, text mining, natural language processing, health care, r package

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